

Migration Dilemma: The Blessing of Incorporation and Isolation Repercussion, Policies Gone Wrong and Miscalculation Of Impact

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Abstract:- The research paper goes into case studies and historical events where migrants were important players on the political and societal scene. The focus of the study covers the ramifications of migrant waves in the third world countries where these communities had the space to influence the host country, in particular fragile political atmosphere. Case studies from Lebanon, a third world country, discuss the country that hosted two distinct migrant waves both moved to the country in the same century having the two groups affecting the nation in very different arguably opposing ways. The definition of the migrants for international institutions and the European approach in addressing migrant issues as well as a suggestion of what makes migration a progressive addition to a country.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Definition of Migration

Migration is the coercive displacement of people from their home country to another country that happens under heavy economic and social pressures coming from the country of origin of the migrant. The UN International Organization of Migration¹ identifies the migrant as follows: "... A person who moves away from his or her place of usual residence within a country or across an international border, temporarily or permanently, and for a variety of reasons". And the UN for refugees and migrants² identifies refugees as: "Refugees are persons who are outside their country of origin for reasons of feared prosecution, conflict, generalized violence, or other circumstances that have seriously disturbed public order and, as a result, require international protection". (UNHCR Statute & the 1951 Convention and regional refugee instruments).

While the refugees require international protections, their lives are entitled to a lot of intervention from the side of international organizations such as the UN and other organizations like the Norwegian Refugee council, Danish refugee council and other institutions... makes them enjoy less liberty and civil rights that gives them the title as refugees. On the other hand, migrants and/or immigrants enjoy more liberty and are not under life threatening circumstances but still live intolerable hard lives that they need to change by moving into another country and secure a better future.

That quality of better social mobility to the migrant makes the society of migrants more influential in the countries they migrated to. After some time, the migrants become eligible to apply for citizenship for the host country of residence, had the migrant been incorporated into the

society and checked certain criteria. By integrating the migrant to the society they can then enjoy political rights and participate in elections, voting, unions etc... That could be seen as a blessing or a curse depending on the right or left political orientation of the questioned person.

B. General Views on Migration

One argument claims that migrants are dangerous because they get into the fabric of society and reshape the identity of the nation and impose unwelcomed lifestyle threatening the tradition of the host country. On the other hand, the other side of the argument claims that immigrants are important to the society because they come with new cultures that can enrich one's own and can fill the gaps in the economy and labor market that was not satisfied by one's own people.

From an economic level, an increase in population can have good and bad effects like having more labor that fills the gaps in lower tier jobs and having the migrants receiving their money in the host country opening bank accounts in the country paying taxes and spending their income in the country, thus boosting the economic cycle. The flip side of the sudden increase in population is having more labor feeding into the labor market, making labor more abundant with cheap labor, which brings down the salaries and having the migrants accepting the lower standard income leaving the host country's own people unemployed, also the sudden increase in population increases the demand on a basic needs like energy, food and beverage, and other services that brings up the prices and causes shortages in these commodities and societal disturbance.

So it is clear that there is a split between the two ideas that is a question left for interpretation for a long time. There have always been good experiments of migration with migrants contributing positively to the country and others where they were a contributing factor to the decline of the state. Here we will discuss how the migrants help the host country and how they hinder the progress of others and what in a general sense can make migration a fruitful opportunity to the state.

II. DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

A. Incidents where migrants were a blessing

The Armenian genocide that took place during the Ottoman rule created a large society of dislocated Armenians that had to migrate to different countries in particular the Middle East. The Armenians in Lebanon for example are a great example of how the migrants can become a very important brick in the societal structure of the host country. It is an example where the migrants are

welcomed into the country are encouraged to integrate in it, impacting politics and economy. The Armenians managed to reshape the camps they initially moved in to into buildings, with the permission of the local authorities, and created an economy within the location they settled in, namely, Burj Hammoud.

This community was well known for their manufacturing skills and handcraft skills and artistry. Armenians had the best quality of clothes, fabrics, shoes all manufactured and sold to the local community in Lebanon. They also have a great reputation in jewelry skills. The Armenians did not keep the prosperity of their work for themselves but now Burj Hammoud is a place where the Lebanese Shia community and the Armenians live peacefully together. This can be traced back to the 1950s and 1960 where the economy of the migrant Armenians became to flourish when unemployment and the political instability and wars in the troubled times in Lebanon, in particular the south, lead the Lebanese from the south to seek comfort in Beirut in particular in Burj Hammoud that was becoming prosperous and offered products and housing a cheap prices (Adrian Hartick, 2016) making the inner migration of the people from south Lebanon to Beirut much more convenient and so having today the mixed communities of Armenians and Lebanese of southern origins in Burj Hammoud at a state of harmony and peace³.

There are also political incidents where the migrant community in Lebanon contributed to peace. The Armenians after recollecting themselves and creating their own small nation within the state had also important influence on the politics in Lebanon that was torn in the Christian-Muslim civil war. The Armenians then did not take side in the war knowing that they belong to the Christian faith but remained neutral. The positive neutrality according to Vera Yacobian, meant being active in support of parties and initiatives that promoted dialogue over conflict a policy that does not mean that the Armenians should disengage themselves in the Lebanese civil war but rather call for peace. This positive involvement of the Armenians was welcomed by the Muslim community in Lebanon, at least the members of which that saw them as a solid bridge to initiate constructive dialogue with the Christian Lebanese that they were at war with⁴ (Yeghia Tashjian, 2020). Today the Armenian community in Lebanon is incorporated into the society and are now the Lebanese-Armenians community a crucial part of the society that if anything served in favor of development for themselves and of Lebanon as a whole. The Armenians had absorbed some of the European mentality and were among the first to bring forward the notion of having political parties that fight for an ideology or a cause. In the more recent years the Armenian community helped in donating for hospitals and for conflict relief especially after the August 4 Beirut Blast and see themselves as true Lebanese citizens as they really are.

B. Migrant Development Capacity

There is a well-known phrase that is “migration and development nexus” that implies the potential of having developmental opportunities in any migrant community.

That is because migrants are striped out of many of their basic and social needs and are looking for them in the host country. And so the migrants come with a lot of demands on commodities and services that create the safe heathen for new projects, investments, and NGOs to work for this community and so bring with them employment and innovation, especially in which individuals of the migrant community are empowered and helped to do these developmental initiatives.

Several benefits come from the migrants from their work in the host country in several forms. They have more appetite to work in the “dirty work” or dangerous work that the citizens of the developed countries will choose not to be involved in and so they create opportunities for investments and growth in the sectors that are deemed of harsh working conditions. Also, the migrants can benefit their country of origin by having some choosing to travel back to the country after gaining skills and professional capabilities and build themselves businesses in their home countries with branches in the country that hosted them and so can propel connections and diplomatic dialogue between the two countries that will bring unseen immediate benefits and cooperation⁵. The diaspora in the host country are closely held together in a manner they keep track of each other’s’ businesses no to fall and so businesses in the host countries are protected by the network of the societies that brought them (Dhananjyan Sriskandarajah, 2005). So that does provide a certain level of assured stability of economic resilience in economic turmoil.

C. Migration Crises in the Middle East

Although many benefits do come from having migrants flow in the county, it is important to note for cases where migration was a big factor in the decline in the political, social, and economic order. Migration becomes particularly difficult to the host countries when it borders the country of origin. It is so because the countries that share the same region are more likely to have migrants stay for a longer time and bring on more migrants especially if they both share the same language, religion and traditions. That becomes dangerous when migrants from authoritative and countries of low standards of living to non-sovereign countries as it creates tremendous political instability (Simona Vizzoli, 2021). That case fits perfectly well with the Lebanese state that was just born and is, with the identity crisis, struggling to decide on its Arab Identity or pan Arab identity. That coincided with the Black September event in Jordan that, prior to the incident, welcomed the Palestinian Liberation Organization (PLO) in the kingdom but started to become a threat of sovereignty to the Jordanian kingdom as being a state within a state⁷ (Henry Kissinger, 1999).

Long story short, a war happened between the Jordanian army and the Palestinian Liberation Organization known as the PLO that lead to the Cairo Agreement that decided to move the PLO to Beirut and with it several Palestinian migrants. Here we know that the PLO is a politically organized group of individuals that have a sovereignty on their own acting within a state as per the Cairo accord, threatening Lebanon’s own security and sovereignty. That was much more felt in Lebanon that,

unlike Jordan, is not a unified politically sovereign state yet but a fragile young state that just got its independence in search of its own identity. The Palestinian migrant crisis back then was one of the most disagreed on topics and a hot spot to start conflict with as what exactly happened with the Ain Al Rumani incident with the famous bus of Palestinians being shot at and killed which was a Spark of the Lebanese civil war that lasted for thirty years between the leftist front (socialist, communists..) and the nationalist front in Lebanon. In this case the large inflow of migrants that are armed fed into the crippling situation of a weak nation. It is also known that the Palestinians started to think of creating alternative countries on the Lebanese territories but that is due to Lebanon not willing to incorporate them into the society and give them national identity cards that gives them equal civic activities. The state of Lebanon was not ready to handle the Palestinian migrants as it had internal struggles that made the inflow turn into security danger.

D. European Migrant Crisis

Another incident when migrants caused a lot of tensions in modern times is the migrant crisis in Europe that has been going on for a decade. It is the large migrant flow from the Middle East to European countries. Amid the uprisings and wars in the Middle East and with the rise and spread of terrorist organizations that left many civilians losing their homes, jobs, security in the battles and conflicts. That created a huge migrant flow towards welcoming Europe. It was mostly from the Syrian asylum seekers that fled away from the war in their home country that mad many leave s there where many Iraqi, Afghan, recently Ukrainian migrants willing to go to Europe. The lives of the migrants became worse particularly when Jordan, Lebanon and Egypt stopped accepting the large migrant inflow with Turkey not giving the migrants the right to work and keeping the migrants at the borders⁸ (Johnathan Zaragoza-Cristiani, 2015).

The migrant crisis was abused by Belorussia under the influx of Russia⁴ (Ellen Loanes). Since Europe advocates human rights and has de-territorialized borders, it created the best condition for the nonstop unregulated migrant flow into the European countries. That has created many problems for the European Union. The large inflow of migrants unwatched brought with it unprecedented mobility of individuals not abiding by sanitary procedures and required quarantine time after traveling thus making Europe as of the end of 2021 fall into one of the most brutal resurgences of coronavirus in the EU. As did many of the right oriented politicians fear the uncertainties that come with the unsupervised migrant inflow. The problem also has a political dimension where the right oriented political party calls for nationalization, anti-migrant policies and closed territorial borders, in particular in Poland where talks of Polish exit from the EU reached its peak during that time. The nationalistic movement challenged the sovereignty of the EU over Poland that is claiming that it is should be who decides who comes to Poland¹⁰ (Jan Cienski, 2017). By 2020, 12 million refugees are recognized in Europe by the UNHCR¹¹. All that sudden inflow of migrants did cause a lot of social and economic distress even in the migrant friendly countries like Germany that hosted the biggest

share of migrants in Europe to the point that it bothered the local communities. But that distress in Europe happened because of the unplanned inflow of the migrants and having Belorussia playing the migrant card to put pressure on EU solidarity. Also COVID-19 pandemic did not help the migrants in their pursuit of asylum. Had these factors not been there, Europe would be better off and more welcoming of the migrants as it once used to be.

III. CONCLUSION

When migration is organized and the number of allowed entries are planned ahead with a sustainable development plan for the migrants, it can be said that migrants will then play a positive contributing factor to the country given that the country is politically stable and is able to hold the burden of the migrant and can manage easing out internal conflicts. Urban development can bring about investment, new small to medium enterprises (SMEs) to work in the country propelling the economic wheel. It is also a crucial factor to have the idea of incorporating the migrants into the society to have them feel a sense of belonging and then would want to work in favor of the local authorities and bring prosperity and a number of potential developmental projects that employ the migrants and the citizens of the county that is known as the migrant and development nexus. Integrating migrants is key to avoid having migrants a political tool to be invested in by other rival states.

So only when well-coordinated and planned will migration be beneficial to the country and it is not always bad. The other benefits come with a cluster of mutual benefits between the host country and the country of origin. The migrants can build connections as the diaspora community in the host country, build a network of functioning businesses and take them back home and maintain good connections with the country that they migrated to and so foster the relationship of the two counties for further potential coordination. In Europe, the US and the first world countries that fear a population gap between the elderly and the young generation can make use of the migrant inflow to repopulate their demographic structure.

Migration is also beneficial for the country of origin where the people get better education in the host countries that are usually first world countries. Like the European policy “solving the root cause of migration” goes about solving migration. It attempts to reshape the country of origin by education, empowering women and making the educated men and women have less children and thus reducing overpopulation in the country of origin while being a more contributing member to the society rather than being pushed to the side. All that contributes in later stages to more pro-democracy countries based on women education and empowerment that in turn educate their children to have a mindset of citizenship thus solving the social issues that come from the malfunctioning system of the country of origin. A step and another EU policy known as the “circular migration”. It is important to have circular migration in a manner that the countries of origin will fear creating more struggles for their own people and stop them from getting

